

3 C185V, 1 V185C

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

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0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 C185V, 1 V185C

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

3 C185V, 1 V185C

● C
● V

■ shallow
■ intermediate
■ deep
■ NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12